

**Designing a Roadmap for
Effective and Sustainable Strategies for
Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of
EU Agriculture to Navigate within a
Safe and Just Operating Space**

**The Impact of Spatial
Competition on Farm Exits: A
Study of the German Agricultural
Sector**

Discussion paper

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1 The Impact of Spatial Competition on Farm Exits: A Study of the German 2 Agricultural Sector¹

3 Abstract

4 This study investigates the role of spatial competition in the land market on farm exit decisions, with a focus on
5 the heterogeneous effects across different farm types, including age groups, legal forms, and specializations.
6 Using a unique dataset from the German Farm Structure Survey (FSS), we develop measures to describe
7 neighbouring spatial competition, including historical growth patterns and dominance in size. Our analysis
8 reveals that increased local competition for land is positively associated with higher exit rates, but that this
9 association is heterogeneous across different farm types and categories, highlighting the importance of
10 considering farm-level interactions in this respect.

11 Keywords: farm structural change; spatial competition; agricultural land market; exit decision; neighbouring
12 interaction

13 1 Introduction

14 The number of farms in the German agricultural sector has decreased drastically, from approximately 470,000 in
15 1999 to 300,000 in 2010, and further to 260,000 in 2020. In contrast, the total productive land for farming has
16 remained relatively stable, decreasing slightly from 17.1 million hectares to 16.6 million over the same period.
17 This implies that land and other factors are transferred from exiting to the remaining farms. Since land cannot
18 be moved, this transfer primarily occurs within local land markets, typically involving geographically close farms.²
19 Storm et al. (2015) accounted for the effects of neighbours using simple indicators to describe the size of
20 neighbourhood farms (e.g., mean neighbour size) and assumed that the neighbouring size effect is the same for

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² See for example Plogmann et al. (2022) for an analysis of the Federal State of Brandenburg, Germany, and Pennerstorfer (2022) for Austria.

21 all farms. These simple measures to describe neighbourhood characteristics might miss important aspects. For
22 instance, for competition in the land market, the mean neighbouring size might be less important than the
23 presence of one or more dominant neighbours. Furthermore, commercial farms may respond differently to
24 competitive pressures than part-time family farms, which may continue operating due to non-pecuniary
25 motivations. Likewise, farms specializing in horticulture may react differently to changes in neighbourhood
26 competition compared to dairy farms. In this study, we aim to determine the extent to which the effects of
27 neighbouring spatial competition are heterogeneous across legal forms, age structures, and farm specializations,
28 and develop appropriate measures to assess farm competition among neighbouring farms.

29 We use the German farm structure survey (FSS) data collected for several years, from 1999 until 2020, covering
30 an average of 340,000 farm enterprises. This unique dataset offers distinct advantages compared to existing
31 studies relying on sample data. The reason that neighbouring effects have not been thoroughly investigated thus
32 far is likely due to the limited availability of spatial information. However, in recent years, agricultural statistics
33 offices have made more spatial information accessible, including postal addresses and the distribution and
34 location of fields. Lastly, studying neighbourhood effects needs a comprehensive sample, not spatially restricted,
35 to analyse the influence of all neighbours, such as the German FSS data. This allows us to go beyond existing
36 studies, and we develop targeted measures to describe neighbouring spatial competition, for example, the
37 distributions of neighbours in terms of their size and past growth pattern, or if there are dominant neighbours.

38 We investigate farmers' decisions about leaving the agricultural sector as a binary choice decision. The model
39 can be conceptualized as a latent utility model. The latent variable represents the utility of the decision to
40 continue or exit the farm business. The farmer's utility is influenced by various factors, including their
41 characteristics, those of neighbouring farms, and regional variables. Our primary objective is to explore the
42 impact of spatial competition in the land market on farm exits. To achieve this, we introduce different proxy
43 variables for competition in the land market. These spatial competition indicators incorporate historical growth
44 data from neighbouring farms and measures of dominance, comparing neighbouring farm sizes to the size of the
45 farmer's operation.

46 This study contributes to the literature on analysing the effects of competition in the local land market on farm
47 exit decisions in two aspects. First, it improves the definition of neighbourhoods to capture spatial interactions
48 and develops spatial variables that measure competition based on the size of neighbouring farms. Second, we
49 also examine how these competitive effects vary across different farm types and assess the representativeness
50 of the findings concerning the broader farm population.

51 Previous studies such as Saint-Cyr et al. (2019) and Paroissien et al. (2021), defined neighbourhoods based on
52 administrative units, resulting in inconsistent neighbourhood sizes and potentially incomplete spatial
53 interactions. Similarly, Plogmann et al. (2022) relied on administrative regions but also incorporated hypothetical
54 farmstead locations based on plot locations, constructing farm-specific neighbourhoods using a 12-km radius.
55 However, administrative unit-based approaches may fail to accurately capture relevant farm-level interactions,
56 as neighbourhood effects tend to weaken with increasing distance between farms. Larger administrative units
57 can dilute these effects. Furthermore, when neighbourhoods are defined strictly by administrative boundaries,
58 as in Saint-Cyr et al. (2019), farms located on either side of a border separating two adjacent units are excluded
59 from each other's neighbourhood effects, leading to potentially inaccurate representations of spatial
60 interactions. Expanding the definition to include adjacent administrative units (Paroissien et al., 2021), can
61 partially address this issue but exacerbates the problem of excessively large neighbourhoods. In contrast, we
62 define neighbourhoods using explicit fixed grid-level information, ensuring uniform neighbourhood sizes and
63 extending neighbourhood effects beyond administrative boundaries. Thereby, we rely on hypothetical
64 farmsteads in the mid-point of the grid. This refined approach provides a more precise representation of spatial
65 dependencies among farms, aligning more closely with Plogmann et al. (2022) and their fixed-radius method
66 around hypothetical farmsteads.

67 Competition in the land market has been analysed using various spatial variables, often focusing on neighbouring
68 farm sizes. Some studies have relied on measures based on average farm size (Paroissien et al., 2021) and
69 deviations from these averages (Saint-Cyr et al., 2019), incorporating additional factors such as profitability and
70 farmers' age. Plogmann et al. (2022) used proxies like farm size inequality (also employed by Saint-Cyr et al.
71 (2019)) and the number of competitors, which vary per farm depending on the farm's individual neighbourhood.
72 Our study goes beyond these measures by introducing spatial competition indicators that account for historical

73 farm growth and dominance within the neighbourhood. Our indicators are farm-specific and based solely on
74 neighbouring farm sizes. Historical farm growth includes size growth information only from neighbours, whereas
75 the dominance indicators include average and maximum farm size in relation to each farm size in consideration.
76 This approach aims to provide a more precise representation of competition dynamics by generating indicators
77 that reflect the competitive environment from the perspective of each individual farm.

78 Understanding how competition affects different types of farms is crucial. Prior research has attempted to
79 differentiate farm responses to competition. Saint-Cyr et al. (2019) employed a mixture model to improve model
80 fit across farm types, thereby allowing for differential effects. Paroissien et al. (2021) analysed differential effects
81 for farms smaller than their average neighbour. Plogmann et al. (2022) primarily assumed homogeneity in
82 neighbourhood effects, only testing for differential impacts on large farms. In our study, we explicitly test for
83 heterogeneous effects by interacting our spatial competition indicators with farm characteristics such as age,
84 specialization, and legal form. This enables us to examine how different types of farms respond to competitive
85 pressures in the land market, thereby contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of spatial
86 dependencies in agriculture. Studying this heterogeneity requires large datasets with sufficient variation in the
87 neighbouring effect. Here, the size of the dataset available in this study has clear advantages compared to
88 previous studies relying on smaller datasets or only samples of farms, for which such an analysis is hardly possible.

89 Saint-Cyr et al. (2019) and Paroissien et al. (2021) utilize comprehensive data on French agricultural farmers, but
90 apply restrictions that limit their analyses to farmers in Brittany or those under the age of 50, respectively.
91 Plogmann et al. (2022) utilize InVeKoS data from the German federal state of Brandenburg. In contrast, we use
92 the German FSS, which covers the entire population of German farms, albeit with specific thresholds for inclusion
93 in the survey. This dataset serves as the basis for all national statistics on farm structures in Germany. While the
94 other studies focus their interpretations on specific subgroups of farms in France or Germany, our findings are
95 representative of the full population of German farms.

96 In this study, we find that there is heterogeneity in the effect of spatial competition on farm exit rates, which
97 substantially differ between types of farms. Additionally, these findings vary depending on the type of spatial
98 competition indicator used. On average, increasing local competition for land is positively associated with higher

99 exit rates. This suggests that higher competition in land markets may drive farm exits. The magnitude of the exit
100 probabilities also differs between farm types and within each category of farm types. Across age groups, there is
101 heterogeneity in the association between exit probabilities and increasing local land competition, irrespective of
102 the indicator used to measure spatial competition. Full-time and part-time sole proprietorship farms exhibit
103 positive but differing magnitudes of exit probabilities, while corporate and partnership farms appear unaffected
104 by spatial competition. Farm specializations show varying associations with exit probabilities, though historical
105 growth patterns are less frequently linked to higher exit probabilities compared to dominance spatial
106 competition indicators related to dominance in size. Distinguishing between different farm specializations and
107 legal forms is crucial, as these categories exhibit distinct exit probabilities due to competition in the land market.
108 By accounting for these differences, we gain insight into how farm types are associated with varying levels of
109 local competition.

110 The subsequent section provides the theoretical background and the construction of proxies for competition in
111 local land markets. Section 3 presents the data used and describes how the neighbourhood is constructed.
112 Section 4 discusses the empirical strategy, Section 5 presents the estimated results, and Section 6 discusses the
113 outcomes. The final section concludes.

114 **2 Measuring neighbourhood effects**

115 In the literature, the average neighbour size (in terms of agricultural land use) of neighbouring farms is often
116 used as a proxy for competition on the land market. Farms compete to secure plots, and larger farms might be
117 more competitive as they can exploit scale effects or are better positioned to adopt new technologies due to
118 improved access to information and financial resources (Goddard et al., 1993; Weiss, 1999) or act as price leaders
119 and pay higher rental rates which translates into higher average land rental prices which might foster exit among
120 remaining farms (Graubner et al., 2021). Hence, regions with larger average farm sizes and unequal distribution
121 of land lead to a higher exit of small farms, as supported by Huettel and Margarian (2009). Larger farm size and
122 unequal distribution of land can be proxied by the presented spatial competition indicators as these recognize
123 not only the own farm size, but also the size of the remaining farms.

124 In a competitive environment, the likelihood of a farm exiting the agricultural sector increases as neighbouring
 125 farms grow larger. We consider two different proxies for land market competition to examine this relationship
 126 (Table 1). The first proxy, which we refer to as the *growth of the others* (growth indicator), attempts to capture
 127 how competitive markets have been historically by examining the growth trends of neighbouring farms from
 128 1999 to 2010. The second proxy, focusing on the *dominant farms in the neighbourhood* (dominance indicator) in
 129 terms of size, aims to assess the current land market competition each farm is facing individually in 2010. Here,
 130 we present two dominance indicators. The first calculates the average agricultural land of neighbouring farms
 131 relative to the size of the farm under consideration. The second measure compares the agricultural land of the
 132 largest farm in the neighbourhood to the size of the farm under consideration.

133 **Table 1. Overview of depicted proxies for land market competition**

Proxies for land market competition		
competition	Description	Interpretation
$Growth1_{in} = \frac{1}{AL_n} \sum_{j \neq i \text{ in } n} \Delta AL_j [> 0]$	<p>ΔAL_j = absolute growth of j farm's agricultural land over time (1999-2010)</p> <p>AL_n the agricultural land of all farms in the neighbourhood n in 2010</p>	<p>The higher the growth variable, the greater the assumed competition in the land market that farm i faces, which is hypothesized to increase the likelihood of exit.</p>
<p><i>Growth of the others</i></p>	<p>It takes all farms in the neighbourhood n other than farm i.</p> <p>Only positive numbers are used.</p> <p>The growth indicator is normalized by the available agricultural land in the neighbourhood.</p>	
<p><i>Dominant farms in the neighbourhood:</i></p>	$Domi2_{in} = \frac{\overline{AL_{n-t}}}{AL_i}$ <p>$\overline{AL_{n-t}}$ is the mean of total agricultural land in the neighbourhood n, except farm i</p>	<p>For each farm i it measures how much the average farm size of the other farms in the neighbourhood n is above or below the farm size of farm i.</p>

Average size of neighbouring farms	where $\overline{AL_{n-i}}$ is normalized by farm size AL_i of farm i in consideration	A value below 1 means that the farm i is larger than the average of remaining farms in the neighbourhood, a value above 1 means that there must be other farms that are larger than farm i .
		The higher the dominance indicator, the greater the assumed competition in the land market that farm i faces, which is hypothesized to increase the likelihood of exit

Largest neighbouring farms	$Domi3_{in} = \frac{\max_{j \in n} AL_j}{AL_i}$	$\max_{j \in n} AL_j$ is the size of the largest farm in the neighbourhood n where $\max_{j \in n} AL_j$ is normalized by farm size AL_i of farm i in consideration	For each farm i , it measures how much larger the farm size of the largest farm in the neighbourhood n is compared to the farm size of farm i . These values are bounded to 1 at the lower end and to the value of the largest farm in the neighbourhood n at the upper end. The higher the dominance indicator, the greater the assumed competition in the land market that farm i faces, which is hypothesized to increase the likelihood of exit
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134 Source: Own compilation.

135 Table 2 illustrates three historical growth scenarios for a neighbourhood.³ The first column depicts five farms
 136 existing within a single neighbourhood. The second column presents the farm sizes in 1999. The following
 137 columns present three historical growth scenarios: the first represents the least growth, the second depicts
 138 medium growth, and the third shows the highest growth. Each growth scenario depicts the size and the absolute
 139 growth rate (ΔAL_j) in one column, while the next column represents the *Growth1* indicator ($Growth1_{in}$). The
 140 bold and italic numbers of the *Growth1* indicator depict farm i that face the highest and lowest pressure from
 141 historical growth. It is assumed that growth occurs as farms take over the land of those who exit. In the low-
 142 growth scenario, one farm exits, and three farms expand by acquiring its land. The same process applies to the
 143 other scenarios. Larger growth rates lead to higher *Growth1* values for each farm.

³ A graphical illustration is depicted in chapter A.2 in the appendix.

144 **Table 2. Illustration of growth scenarios for one neighbourhood from 1999 to 2010 with different growth rates**
 145 **and farm numbers**

Farm	Initial size (1999)	Scenarios in 2010					
		Low growth		Medium growth		High growth	
		Size (growth rate)	<i>Growth1</i>	Size (growth rate)	<i>Growth1</i>	Size (growth rate)	<i>Growth1</i>
1	20	0 (-20)		0 (-20)		0 (-20)	
2	25	30 (5)	0,067	0 (-25)		0 (-25)	
3	55	60 (5)	0,067	75 (20)	0,111	0 (-55)	
4	50	50 (0)	0,089	50 (0)	0,200	50 (0)	0,444
5	75	85 (10)	0,044	100 (25)	0,089	175 (100)	0,000

146 Source: Own compilation.

147 Table 3 illustrates six hypothetical neighbourhood scenarios, each differing in the number of farms and farm sizes
 148 within the neighbourhood. Next to each farm, the values for the farm size and the dominance indicators
 149 ($Domi2_{in}$ and $Domi3_{in}$) are displayed. Farms of the same size share the same dominance indicators. The
 150 assumption is that higher dominance indicators correspond to greater competitive pressure in the land market
 151 due to the presence of dominant farms in the neighbourhood, which in turn increases the likelihood of farm exit.
 152 Neighbourhoods 1 and 3 illustrate a dominant (highly competitive) land market situation. According to our
 153 indicators, the six smaller farms in neighbourhood 1 receive relatively high values for both land market
 154 dominance indicators, indicating higher competitive pressure. In contrast, the largest farm in these
 155 neighbourhoods receives a very low value for each dominance indicator, reflecting its dominant position in the
 156 land market with minimal competition from neighbouring farms.

157 **Table 3. Illustration dominance scenarios in three neighbourhoods with relatively higher dominance situations,**
 158 **with different farm sizes and numbers**

Neighbourhood d	Higher dominance				Lower dominance					
	Farm	Size	Domi2	Domi3	Neighbourhood	Farm	Size	Domi2	Domi3	
1	1	100	0,09	1,00	4	17	20	2,56	3,75	
	2	9	2,69	11,11		18	25	2,00	3,00	
	3	9	2,69	11,11		19	55	0,77	1,36	
	4	9	2,69	11,11		20	50	0,88	1,50	
	5	9	2,69	11,11		21	75	0,50	1,00	
	6	9	2,69	11,11		5	22	25	1,23	1,60
	7	9	2,69	11,11		23	35	0,83	1,14	
2	8	60	0,63	1,00	24	30	1,00	1,33		
	9	55	0,72	1,09	25	20	1,58	2,00		
	10	50	0,83	1,20	26	40	0,71	1,00		
	11	9	6,11	6,67	27	28	1,08	1,43		
3	12	220	0,26	1,00	28	32	0,93	1,25		
	13	200	0,31	1,10	6	29	100	1,00	1,00	
	14	9	12,17	24,44	30	100	1,00	1,00		
	15	9	12,17	24,44	31	100	1,00	1,00		
	16	9	12,17	24,44	32	100	1,00	1,00		
					33	100	1,00	1,00		
					34	100	1,00	1,00		
					35	100	1,00	1,00		

159 Source: Own compilation.

160 Neighbourhoods 2 and 4 differ somewhat from the others in terms of land market structure. Neighbourhood 5
 161 is diverse but lacks truly dominant farms, while in neighbourhood 6, all farms are of equal size. In neighbourhood

162 5, values for both dominance indicators are relatively evenly distributed. However, the largest farm has a
163 $Domi2_{in}$ value of 0.71 and a $Domi3_{in}$ value of 1, whereas the smallest farm has the highest values of 1.58 and
164 2, respectively. Overall, the competitive situation based on farm size is captured well. Still, the extremes in
165 dominance values are notably different from those in neighbourhoods 1 and 3, where smaller farms experience
166 much stronger competitive pressure.

167 The range of land market proxy values is significantly larger in neighbourhoods where historical farm growth has
168 been higher or where some farms dominate others in size. These indicators aim to effectively reflect land market
169 conditions, highlighting situations in which one or more farms hold a dominant position and therefore exert
170 greater competitive pressure.

171 A key hypothesis of the paper is that spatial competition is important, but that the effect it has on the farm exit
172 decision differs between different types of farms. At first, we can observe that farm exit rates as such vary by
173 farm type. For example, studies in the US have found that farms specialized in beef production tend to have
174 lower exit rates (Mishra et al., 2010). In contrast, cash crop and hog farms exhibit higher exit rates than beef
175 farms (Hoppe and Korb, 2006). The study of Paroissien et al. (2021) also showed varying exit probabilities of
176 several farm specializations, especially when interacting with the farm size. Unfortunately, they did not consider
177 farm specialization about neighbouring farm sizes. Table 9 in chapter A.1 in the appendix provides descriptive
178 evidence of the data used to differentiate the effects in this study. It is showing different unconditional exit
179 probabilities across farm type categories. Beginning with farm specializations, specialist crop farms have higher
180 exit rates than specialist animal or mixed farms. Farm specialization evaluates a farm's productive focus based
181 on its standard output values.⁴ We classify farming into the general type of farming, which consists of eight
182 specializations.⁵ Since these specializations vary significantly in their production activities, they also vary in
183 investment horizons, land and machinery usage, and their correlation with land market indicators. These

⁴ For a description: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Farm_typology: "Farm specialisation describes the trend towards a single dominant activity in farm income: an agricultural holding is said to be specialised when a particular activity provides at least two thirds of the production or the business size of an agricultural holding."

⁵ The general farm types describing the farm specialization are: (1) specialist field crops, (2) specialist horticulture, (3) specialist permanent crops, (4) specialist grazing livestock, (5) specialist granivores, (6) mixed cropping, (7) mixed livestock holdings and (8) mixed crops-livestock.

184 differences also lead to varying sunk costs, opportunity costs, and exposure to market and weather risks. For
185 example, a newly built stable represents a sunk cost for a farm specialized in dairy farming, as it is challenging to
186 sell it if the farmer decides to exit the sector. All these aspects might lead to heterogeneity in how farms respond
187 to neighbouring competition. While the opportunity costs of alternative employment outside farming are likely
188 similar across specializations, the decision to become a more specialized crop farm rather than maintaining a
189 mixed-farming approach also involves opportunity costs.

190 Additionally, market risks, such as fluctuations in input prices, can increase production costs that may not always
191 be fully passed on to buyers. Weather risks also play a role, as adverse conditions—such as droughts—may have
192 a more severe impact on crop farms than on livestock farms. All these production decisions involve
193 considerations about how to utilize agricultural land. For instance, investing in new machinery for harvesting
194 crops or applying fertilizers and pesticides may be accompanied by acquiring additional land to improve
195 scalability or consolidate existing plots, both of which can reduce costs. Similarly, a dairy farm planning to invest
196 in a new stable may also decide to expand its pasture area. In both cases, the farmer is likely to evaluate the need
197 for additional agricultural land. These considerations underscore the importance of distinguishing between farm
198 specializations when examining their relationships with the defined spatial competition indicators.

199 The legal form divides the farms into family and non-family farms. Family farms are sole proprietorship farms,
200 which are further divided into full-time and part-time operations. Non-family farms are divided into corporate
201 and partnership farms. As these legal forms are very different from each other, they might also be very differently
202 associated with the spatial competition indicators. For instance, corporate farms might have better access to
203 credits, which makes them also stronger players in the land market, as they may pay more for rental land
204 (Graubner et al., 2021). They might also pay less than non-corporate farms (Ciaian and Swinnen, 2006) using their
205 competitive position against landlords. On the other hand, corporate farms might be less interested in keeping
206 the business alive if circumstances change, and hence, give up or sell their business. They may also view their
207 business as less emotional than family farms or have less interest in passing it on to their children. Family farms,
208 especially part-time farms, which are smaller, have already experienced a decline in numbers, which may be
209 connected to the fact that larger and corporate farms have expanded (Kay et al., 2015). Table 9 shows that part-

210 time farms have higher unconditional exit rates than the other types of legal forms. These situations and different
211 motivations are not readily observable, but the legal form differentiation may reveal different associations.

212 The differentiation of age groups of farm holders will be categorized into young farmers, middle-aged farmers,
213 and farmers nearing retirement. Table 9 shows descriptive evidence that the oldest age group has the highest
214 exit rate. This is clear, as these farmers are closer to retirement. Even though all these age groups might also
215 have different motivations for keeping up farming, and therefore might be differently associated with the spatial
216 competition indicators. Younger farmers get additional payments for some time after taking over or starting a
217 farm; they might also be more risk-taking, but also less viable for investments (EIP-AGRI Focus Group, 2016).
218 Young farmers, whether they are entrants (which is outside the scope of this paper) or new to the business, may
219 face difficulties in acquiring land and establishing a well-run business (Kay et al., 2015). They also have longer
220 planning horizons, but might be less reluctant to change occupation. Middle-aged farmers may be experienced
221 enough and have a medium planning horizon, which makes this group suitable for competitiveness in the land
222 market. There is evidence that this group is more frequently in a growth phase and, consequently, more active
223 in the land market compared to other age groups (Viira et al., 2013). Farms in the oldest age group, should be
224 competitive, and, depending on whether a successor is available, be differently responsive to land market
225 competition. Overall, it is unclear in which direction the spatial competition indicators are associated with farm
226 exit for different age groups.

227 **3 Data and variable construction**

228 This section presents and describes the data used for the estimation. The first subsection explains how our
229 dependent variable, the exit variable, is derived. The second subsection details the construction of the
230 neighbourhood, drawing on suggestions from the literature and the suitability of the data. The third subsection
231 presents descriptive statistics for the spatial competition indicators we have constructed. Descriptive statistics
232 of the additional control variables are provided in the appendix.⁶

⁶ See the tables in Chapter A.1 in the appendix.

233 The primary data source for this study is Germany's FSS.⁷ We have access to seven complete surveys from 1999
234 to 2020, with the most recent one conducted in 2020.⁸ We use the years 1999, 2003, 2007 and 2010 to compile
235 all the farm level variables, including the spatial competition indicators, used in the models and additionally the
236 year 2020 to capture the exit decision of the farm holder.⁹

237 **3.1 Number of exits**

238 In the FSS, each farm gets a unique identifier. We observe the exit or stay-in-business decision of farmers
239 between 2010 and 2020. If the identifier is observed in 2010, but not in 2020, the farm exited the sector, and the
240 exit variable equals one. Conversely, if the identifier is observed in 2020, the farmer stays in business, and the
241 exit variable equals zero. However, there might be other reasons why the identifier is not observed in 2020. First,
242 the farm is merged with one or more other farms, and hence, only one of these farms keeps the identifier.
243 Second, it is also possible that a farm is dissolved after 2010, but is re-founded before 2020, receiving a new
244 identifier. This may not be a genuine exit from the sector, but we cannot control for that, and in our case, we
245 define those farms as having exited. Third, a farm might be so small that it is near the lower thresholds of being
246 covered in the survey. Hence, a farm observed in 2010 may have fallen below the minimum requirements in the
247 years leading up to 2020 and was therefore not surveyed, even though it remained in business.

248 In 2010, the FSS consisted of 299,134 farm surveys. From these, 229,364 farms were still active in 2020, meaning
249 that 69,770 exited the survey. This gives an exit rate of 23.3%. Figure 1 shows the distribution of farm exits across
250 the NUTS 2 regions in Germany. One can see that the exit rates are not evenly distributed. Most exits are
251 observed in the North and South-West of Germany, whereas the smallest exit rates are observed in the South.

252

⁷ Throughout the paper we call the German agricultural data FSS, which stands for farm structure survey. The years 2003, 2007 and 2016 are full population surveys, but some variables are surveyed only for sample farms. They are called "farm structure surveys" ("Agrarstrukturerhebung"). 1999, like 2010 and 2020, is an "agricultural census", generally capturing more variables for all farms.

⁸ The farms must be active and reach a certain threshold for some structural features to be part of the survey.

⁹ The survey year 2016 was not used in our analysis.

264 which means that areas are considered "connected" if they share a border at any point, including corners. The
265 dark grey (d) and the blue circle (e) describe an area of about 5 and 12 kilometres around the farm, respectively.
266 The red squares (c) describe neighbouring farms within the green squares, and an additional Queen contiguity
267 around the green squares.

268
269 **Figure 2. Scheme of neighbouring areas around the hypothesized farmstead of a farm**

270 Source: Own compilation.

271 Considering different neighbourhood sizes, in the German federal state of Brandenburg, 90% of the farms have
272 newly acquired farm plots within 12 kilometres and 65% within 5 kilometres (Plogmann et al., 2022) of their
273 farmsteads (depicted by the blue and dark grey circles, respectively). In Bavaria, approximately 90% of the farms
274 have their plots within 5 kilometres (Machl, 2016), which is depicted by the dark grey circle. Both federal states
275 are cases from the lower and upper parts of the distribution of farm sizes. The average farm size in terms of total
276 agricultural land in 2020 of Brandenburg (242 hectares) is almost 6 times larger than that of Bavaria (37 hectares)
277 (Statistisches Bundesamt, 2021). Farmers typically prefer land close to their farmsteads (Bakker et al., 2018;
278 Grammatikopoulou et al., 2013; Jänicke and Müller, 2024; Latruffe and Piet, 2014). Moreover, an Austrian study
279 concludes that proximity of farmsteads between farms that exit and farms that take over the land is essential
280 (Pennerstorfer, 2022). Therefore, we suggest that farms within the 5x5 kilometres grid cell (the single green

281 rectangle in the middle), as well as farms in the adjoining green squares, can be considered relevant in terms of
 282 influences from neighbouring farms. Our neighbourhood definition is between both the extreme examples of
 283 distances between farmsteads and fields described above (dark grey and blue circles). We therefore expect that
 284 most neighbouring effects should be measurable within the grid cell or in the adjoining squares (green area).

285 3.3 Spatial competition indicators

286 Table 4 provides descriptive statistics of the spatial competition indicators. It provides mean and standard
 287 deviation as well as the 10th, 25th, median, 75th and 90th percentiles for farms that stay in business and exit. They
 288 differ in scale based on their definitions. It is evident that, on average, all indicators are larger for exiting farms.
 289 Additionally, as the range of the indicators increases, the standard deviation increases.

290 **Table 4. Descriptive distributional statistics of the spatial competition indicators**

Spatial competition		Standard		Percentiles				
indicator	Group	Mean	Deviation	10th	25th	Median	75th	90th
Growth of the others (Growth1)	Stayed	0.19	0.04	0.14	0.17	0.19	0.22	0.24
	Exited	0.20	0.04	0.15	0.17	0.20	0.22	0.24
Average size of neighbouring farms	Stayed	3.65	13.23	0.41	0.66	1.26	2.83	6.20
	Exited	9.50	24.25	0.90	1.67	3.60	7.89	20.85
Largest neighbouring farm (Domi3)	Stayed	38.02	152.65	2.65	4.56	9.90	24.71	65.12
	Exited	100.22	270.70	6.05	12.19	28.67	79.79	242.78

291 Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI:
 292 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0; DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

293 Figure 3 visualizes the information in Table 4 and provides a detailed comparison of the distributional moments
 294 for each of the farm types considered in the analysis. Each column presents one of the indicators, and each row
 295 presents a farm type category. The x-axis presents the values of each indicator, and the points depict the 10th,
 296 25th, mean, median, 75th and 90th percentiles, and the line connecting the 10th and 90th percentiles. For instance,
 297 the *Growth1* indicator values for “Age category 1) years <= 40” range from around 0.14 to 0.24 with a mean of
 298 0.19.

299

300 **Figure 3. Distributional moments of the spatial competition indicators**

301 Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI:
 302 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

303 When examining age categories, the distribution of the growth indicator appears relatively stable across all three
 304 groups, with the mean and median values closely aligned, indicating a symmetric distribution. The spread
 305 between the 10th and 90th percentiles suggests moderate variability, meaning that farms across all age
 306 categories face similar levels of historical neighbouring farm growth. However, for the dominance indicators,
 307 there is substantial dispersion, particularly among older farmers, where the 90th percentile extends significantly
 308 beyond the median. This suggests that some older farmers operate in regions where neighbouring farms,
 309 especially the largest ones, are considerably larger than their own. This may indicate that older farmers are more
 310 likely to face intense competition from dominant farms in their vicinity.

311 For different farm specializations, the growth indicator remains relatively uniform across the two groups of
 312 specializations. Field crops, horticulture, grazing livestock, and mixed crops and livestock farms show a larger
 313 dispersion than the others. However, the dominance indicators show much wider spreads, particularly for
 314 horticulture and permanent crop farms. The large gap between the 10th and 90th percentiles in these categories

315 suggests that some farms face competition from significantly larger neighbours, while others operate in a more
316 balanced competitive environment.

317 Regarding legal form of farms, full-time and part-time farms exhibit similar and relatively high values for the
318 neighbouring growth indicator. In contrast, corporate farms show a wider range but lower average values.
319 Regarding the dominance indicators, full-time farms have a smaller range of values, while the range is larger for
320 other legal forms, particularly corporate farms. However, in terms of the median, part-time farms have the
321 highest values. This suggests that while the majority of corporate and partnership farms operate in environments
322 with relatively equal competitors in lower competitive environments, others are situated in areas where a single
323 dominant farm strongly overshadows them, creating a highly competitive landscape.

324 Overall, the figure highlights distinct competitive dynamics faced by farms depending on their age category, farm
325 specialization, and legal form. *Growth1* appears to be more stable across groups, indicating that historical
326 neighbouring farm growth may not have a drastically different competitive impact. However, *Domi2* and *Domi3*
327 reveal that competition from larger farms is highly variable, especially among older farmers, horticulture and
328 permanent farms, and corporate farms. The wide spread in the upper percentiles for certain groups suggests
329 that some farms operate in areas with intense competitive pressure, while others face more balanced conditions.

330 **4 Empirical strategy**

331 Our strategy assesses the relationship between our spatial competition indicators and the likelihood of farms
332 remaining in or exiting the sector. We recognize that these indicators are unevenly distributed among farms and
333 that we do not account for all factors influencing the exit decision. Making causal statements in this context is
334 inherently challenging, even on a conceptual level. Another key aspect is that competition in the land market and
335 past developments are closely linked to the individual farm, which arises from the limited and relatively fixed
336 amount of agricultural land available in the local market. Therefore, we view our estimates as conditional
337 associations instead of causal relationships. They offer descriptive evidence on the relationships found in the
338 data. When the estimated coefficients are positive and both statistically and economically significant, they
339 illustrate the temporal co-occurrence of spatial competition and the exit decision.

340 We use a logit model to represent the farmer's decision to exit. The utility of remaining in or leaving the farm
341 business is represented by the latent variable $Exit_i^*$ and is influenced by its characteristics, those of its
342 neighbouring farms, or regional variables.

343 $Exit_i^*$ is the latent variable of interest that determines the farmer's decision to exit the business. The exit variable
344 is defined:

$$exit_i = 1 \text{ if } Exit_i^* > 0 \text{ and } exit_i = 0 \text{ if } Exit_i^* \leq 0 \quad (1)$$

345 where $exit_i$ is the observed situation of the farm i in 2020, and $exit_i = 1$ indicates that the farm exited the
346 sector, while $exit_i = 0$ means it is still in business. In general, the conditional exit probability is denoted by:

$$P(exit_i = 1|x_i, \beta) = \sigma(x_i\beta) = \frac{\exp(x_i\beta)}{1 + \exp(x_i\beta)} \quad (2)$$

347 where σ is the standard logistic function.

348 It can be written as the logarithm of the odds (log odds):

$$\log\left(\frac{P(exit_i = 1|x_i, \beta)}{1 - P(exit_i = 1|x_i, \beta)}\right) = x_i\beta + \epsilon_i \quad (3)$$

349 where β is estimated in a linear regression of log odds of the probability of exiting the business over staying in
350 business on x_i , the vector of individual, neighbouring and regional covariates and ϵ_i is the error term. A
351 correlation indicated by a statistically significant element of β suggest that, on average, higher competition on
352 the land market (or a certain individual or regional characteristic) corresponds to higher exit rates. If these
353 associations are heterogeneous across farm types, this would indicate that farm types should be interpreted and
354 treated differently. Together with the spatial competition indicators without interaction, we include in equation
355 3 interactions separately with each of the three farm types (farm specialization, age group, and legal form),
356 resulting in a total of twelve models (see Table 5). Three models in the no interaction group, and each farm type
357 (specialization, age group, and legal form) interacts with each of the three spatial competition indicators. All
358 models have the same control variables added, including the farm type categories.

359 **Table 5. Overview of estimation models and their inclusion of the spatial competition indicators and farm type**
 360 **interactions**

Model	Model group	Spatial competition indicator	Interaction groups				Controls	
			No interaction	Age group	Legal forms	Farm specializations	All farm types	Other
1	No interaction	Growth1	Yes				Yes	Yes
2		Domi2	Yes				Yes	Yes
3		Domi3	Yes				Yes	Yes
4	Age group	Growth1		Yes			Yes	Yes
5		Domi2		Yes			Yes	Yes
6		Domi3		Yes			Yes	Yes
7	Legal forms	Growth1			Yes		Yes	Yes
8		Domi2			Yes		Yes	Yes
9		Domi3			Yes		Yes	Yes
10	Farm	Growth1				Yes	Yes	Yes
11	specialization	Domi2				Yes	Yes	Yes
12		Domi3				Yes	Yes	Yes

361 Source: Own compilation.

362 In each of the models, individual explanatory variables are included as control variables. By using estimation
 363 models with additional control variables, we aim to condition as much as possible, given data limitations, the
 364 magnitude of the associations with local market competition and thereby separate out part of the context. This
 365 approach allows us to discuss the strength of relationships between our spatial competitive indicators while
 366 controlling for other factors. For instance, total agricultural land use (farm size) is consistently found to be
 367 negatively correlated with exit probability. Farm size is related to our spatial competition indicator, and
 368 neglecting to consider it could result in biased estimates. Other variables in the literature may not be linked to
 369 our spatial competition indicators and are unlikely to cause collider bias. We incorporate these variables as
 370 previous research indicates they significantly influence farm exit. Their inclusion may improve the precision of
 371 our estimates by reducing error. The literature identified several farm level structural variables like the amount

372 of agricultural land use, herd size or livestock units, ratio of rented land and profit indicators like the standard
373 gross margin of the farm, productive orientation (conventional vs. organic farming), specialization and legal form
374 (Breustedt and Glauben, 2007; Dong et al., 2016; Landi et al., 2016; Paroissien et al., 2021; Saint-Cyr et al., 2019;
375 Zorn and Zimmert, 2022) as well as regional variables like average compensation of employees, disposable
376 income, unemployment rates and population density (Breustedt and Glauben, 2007; Dong et al., 2016; Foltz,
377 2004; Kitenge, 2022; Saint-Cyr et al., 2019; Zorn and Zimmert, 2022). Further, we add demographic variables
378 such as education and age of the farmer as well as NUTS 2 regional dummies (Corsi et al., 2021; Mishra et al.,
379 2010; Piet et al., 2012; Ramsey et al., 2019; Saint-Cyr et al., 2019; Zorn and Zimmert, 2022).

380 **5 Results**

381 Our presentation of results is distinguished between homogenous (“no interaction”) and heterogeneous
382 (“interaction”) effects. We first estimate for each spatial competition indicator a model without any interactions.
383 The heterogeneous effects are then based on interaction terms between all spatial competition indicators and
384 farm specialization, age group and legal forms, separately. We illustrate the estimated relationships by deriving
385 predicted exit probabilities over a range of values from the distribution of the spatial competition indicators to
386 get a better understanding of the level and magnitude of the homogeneous and heterogeneous associations.

387 The predicted exit probabilities are based on the summary statistics of the data we used for the estimation. For
388 instance, to calculate the estimated exit probability for one of the spatial competition indicators, we take 100
389 evenly distributed values of such a spatial competition indicator between the 10th and 90th percentiles of the
390 entire farm population. The remaining continuous variables of the model are held at their (weighted) mean
391 values.¹¹ The categorical variables are treated as follows: we calculate exit probabilities for all combinations of
392 categories as a weighted average according to the number of observations in each category for each of the 100
393 values of the spatial competition indicator. As it is very likely that not all combinations of different categorical
394 variables exist, the predicted exit probabilities must be analysed in comparison to each other and not seen as the
395 true exit probabilities in magnitude. This means that the slope of the curve gives a good representation of the

¹¹ They are weighted by the share of continuing and exiting farms.

396 influence in magnitude, but the intercept—or the area in which the curve is located on the y-axis—is only an
397 approximation of the true one. Therefore, we state these predictions as “based on pseudo-weighted country
398 average”.

399 In Figure 4, we show the difference in the predicted exit probability between low and high competition in the
400 local land market measured by our spatial competition indicators.¹² We plot the percentage point difference (dot)
401 and 95% prediction intervals (error bars) in predicted exit probability between the 10th (low competition) and
402 90th percentiles (high competition) of each spatial competition indicator, with the 10th percentile serving as the
403 reference point for these calculations. Panel A of Figure 4 shows the “no interaction” and the interaction models
404 for the age groups and legal forms, and Panel B shows the farm specialization interaction models. First of all, one
405 can see that the majority of the prediction intervals of the exit probability differences do not include zero.
406 Second, the magnitude and the variability of the probability differences are higher across the farm
407 specializations, followed by the legal forms.

¹² The predicted probability curves can be found in Chapter A.3 in the appendix. They effectively illustrate the level and slope of the exit probability for each spatial competition indicator.

408

409 **Figure 4. Percentage point difference in predicted exit probability between the 10th and 90th percentiles of**
 410 **the spatial competition indicators**

411 Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI:
 412 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

413 For the “no interaction” case—by not considering any specific farm type—the exit probability for a farm facing a
 414 high value for the growth indicator “growth of the others” (*Growth1*) at the 90th percentile is on average
 415 2.62 percentage points (95% prediction interval (PI): 0.33 p.p to 4.92 p.p) higher than for a farm facing a lower

416 value at the 10th percentile. For the dominance indicator “average size of neighbouring farms” (*Domi2*) it is
417 3.56 p.p (PI: [1.28 p.p, 5.84 p.p]) and for the other dominance indicator “largest neighbouring farm” (*Domi3*) it
418 is 3.01 p.p (PI: [0.73 p.p, 5.28 p.p]).¹³ For the farm type interaction group models, the predicted exit probability
419 differences are much more diverse. For instance, the oldest age group specific exit probability difference for
420 *Domi2* is 4.82 p.p [1.77 p.p; 7.88 p.p], for the corporate farms the difference for *Domi3* is 0.93 p.p [-
421 2.63 p.p; 4.49 p.p] and for specialist horticulture farms the difference for *Growht1* is
422 8.33 p.p [4.86 p.p; 11.81 p.p]. To provide context, the unconditional descriptive exit rate for the period from
423 2010 to 2020 is approximately 23%. This indicates that the differences in average exit probabilities for farms
424 operating under varying levels of land market competition are also economically substantial.

425 This summarizes as follows: The prediction intervals of the probability differences of the “no interaction” model
426 do not include zero, which shows that the exit probabilities are higher if the spatial competition indicators a farm
427 faces are higher on average. In other words, it means that in a neighbourhood in which there has been a higher
428 growth of other farms in the past, this is associated with a higher exit probability. For the dominance indicators,
429 if the size of the neighbouring farms is larger or if there is a very large farm, on average, it is also associated with
430 a higher exit probability. For the “no interaction” models, the prediction intervals look similar across the spatial
431 competition indicators. For the farm type interaction group models, the predicted exit probability differences
432 are much more diverse. For some specific farm type categories, the exit probabilities are much higher under
433 higher levels of competition in the land market, while others are not economically different.

434 **6 Discussion**

435 In essence, the results highlight that the impact of land market competition on farm exits is not uniform but
436 varies significantly based on the farm's legal structure and its specialized production system, particularly for older
437 farm holders. This result is important as it confirms our hypothesis that the spatial competition indicators show
438 different associations across farm types with the farm's decision to exit farm business. Table 6 summarizes the

¹³ The predicted exit probability differences are also depicted in tables in Chapter A.4 in the appendix. They also include the continues control variables, which are also part of comparable figures.

439 main findings and shows for the different interaction effects (“no interaction”, “Age Group”, “Legal Form”, and
440 “Farm Specialization”) in column one the main differences within the interactions (interaction groups column)
441 for the growth and dominance indicators (third and fourth column) together or separated.

442 The “**no interaction**” model shows that the spatial competition indicators are associated with very similar
443 increases in exit probabilities, but for the dominance indicators, it is slightly higher. For the average farm, higher
444 competition in the land market is associated with a higher exit probability in the medium term. The exit
445 probability is 2.6%- to 3.6%-points higher on average between very low and very high (e.g., 10th and 90th
446 percentiles—see above) competition in the land market. This strong change in the competition accounts for an
447 increase in the average exit probability by about 11.3% to 15.6%.

448 The **age-group** interaction model shows similar prediction intervals to the “no interaction” model, although the
449 association is stronger and the difference in the exit probabilities is higher in magnitude for the oldest age group.
450 For the younger and middle-aged groups, the interaction terms seem to reveal no economically different effects
451 between them. Although the oldest farm group also has a higher base exit probability, it appears to be strongly
452 associated with higher spatial competition indicators. This could be due to the fact that the farm is near
453 retirement, at least if there is no successor, and if it experiences neighbouring farm growth or has large farms or
454 one large farm in the neighbourhood, it decreases the utility of staying in business even more. This means that
455 higher competition for a farm in the land market can increase structural change—more farms are exiting, and
456 other farms take over the released agricultural area, thereby increasing the average size of the remaining farms.

457 The interactions with **legal forms** show a different pattern compared to the estimated models above. The legal
458 forms are very different from each other, ranging from sole proprietorship (family) farms to corporate and
459 partnership farms. The sole proprietorship farms are associated with almost all spatial competition indicators,
460 while the corporate and partnership farms are not at all. For the full-time sole proprietorship farm, a high growth
461 of the neighbouring farms in the past is associated with a larger difference in the exit probability, while for part-
462 time farms, this is only slightly the case. If the average size of the neighbouring farms is relatively high, a higher
463 difference in the exit probability is indicated, but to a lower extent compared to the growth indicator. For the
464 part-time farms, the difference in the exit probability is largest among the legal forms. The predicted difference

465 in exit probability of the dominant indicator *Domi3* includes zero in the prediction interval, whereas for the part-
466 time farm, it is positive and also large in magnitude. Full- and part-time sole proprietorship farms show some
467 inverse associations, in which full-time farms seem to be affected by past growth in the neighbourhood, but only
468 slightly or not at all by the size of the average or the largest farm in the neighbourhood. The part-time farm is
469 only marginally affected by past growth, but much strongly by both the dominance indicators. For the corporate
470 and partnership farms, all intervals of exit probability differences include zero. The intervals are also much wider
471 for corporate farms than for the other legal forms. This means that considering interaction effects across legal
472 forms is helpful, as it shows that the sole proprietorship farms are associated with some of the spatial
473 competition indicators, and the others are not. For the corporate and partnership farms, it might be the case
474 that those farms are more viable on average to withstand competitive situations in the land market. This is also
475 in line with literature that states advantages in the land market for corporate farms (Ciaian and Swinnen, 2006;
476 Graubner et al., 2021).

477 Regarding the interaction models with **farm specializations**, for FT 5 specialist granivores the predicted
478 probability differences are similar across the spatial competition indicators. For all the other specializations, the
479 growth indicator *Growth1* always shows different strong associations compared to the dominance spatial
480 competition indicators. If there is a strong association with the growth indicator, the association with the
481 dominance indicators is less strong or even null, and vice versa. The growth indicator is very different from the
482 dominance measures. Although the no-interaction effects are similar between the spatial competition indicators,
483 the differences between them are apparent when taking into account the farm's specialization. For the growth
484 indicator, FT 2 specialist horticulture, FT 4 specialist grazing livestock and FT 5 do not include zero in the
485 prediction intervals of exit probability differences. For FT 2, the association is strongest among those, but it also
486 has a wide interval. For the remaining specializations, there seems to be no association of the growth indicator
487 *Growth1* with the exit probability. For the dominance indicators, if there is a strong association, it is often
488 stronger for the average size of the neighbourhood farms (*Domi2*) than if there is one very large farm (*Domi3*).
489 The strongest association is found for FT 1 specialist field crop farms with an almost 15%-point difference of the
490 exit probability if the average size of the neighbourhood farms (*Domi2*) is very large, followed by FT 8 mixed
491 crops and livestock farms and FT 3 permanent crops farms with over 10%-point difference of the exit probability.

492 For the dominance indicator *Domi3*, FT 1, FT 3, and FT 6 mixed-crop farms have the highest difference in exit
493 probability. Across all farm specializations, both the dominance spatial competition indicators seem to have a
494 stronger association on the exit probabilities than the growth indicator. It is only FT 2 that shows the inverse, and
495 FT 5 has very low or slightly null associations. The farm specializations themselves are sometimes similar and
496 sometimes different for some specific farm characteristics. On the one hand, the first five farm specializations
497 are specialist farms and have rather narrow production systems, whereas the remaining farm specializations
498 have a mix of specialist production systems.

499 The analysis of heterogeneous effects shows that different farm types are affected differently by competition in
500 the land market. However, the same does not hold for the age structure of farms. To the best of our knowledge,
501 there are no other studies examining the heterogeneous effects of spatial competitive situations like ours.
502 Considering the most similar indicators of spatial competition by using the size of neighbouring farms,
503 heterogeneous effects have been estimated in Saint-Cyr et al. (2019) and Paroissien et al. (2021). Saint-Cyr et al.
504 (2019) found that business-oriented farms are influenced by larger neighbouring farms, where some of them are
505 negatively affected and can be described as being in a competitive environment. The other business-oriented
506 farms are positively affected and might receive positive spillovers. The remaining farms are described as non-
507 pecuniary motivated farms and are not influenced at all. Compared to our differentiation across legal forms, part-
508 time farms might be associated with rather non-pecuniary farms, and the other legal forms with business-
509 oriented ones. Our results are therefore inverse, because the exit decision of part-time farms is strongly
510 associated with a competitive environment, and business-oriented farms are only slightly (full-time farmers) or
511 not at all (corporate and partnership farms) associated with a competitive situation. Paroissien et al. (2021) also
512 detected different effects, where farms smaller than the average neighbourhood farm had an increased exit
513 probability through competitive effects, and farms larger than the average neighbourhood farm decreased exit
514 probabilities through agglomeration benefits. Both our dominance indicators are similar to those of Paroissien
515 et al. (2021), because of incorporating neighbourhood farm size relative to own farm size. But they are hardly
516 comparable, as their distinction between small and large farms is binary, whereas our indicators are continuous.
517 We can only confirm heterogeneous findings, but only competitive effects, and no agglomeration effects.

518 **Table 6. Summary of the main findings of the estimated effects**

Interaction	Farm type	Growth Indicator Specifics	Dominance Indicators Specifics
groups	categories		
No interaction		Dominance indicators are slightly stronger associated with exit probability than the growth indicator.	
Age Group	Oldest Age Group	Shows a stronger association with both spatial competition indicators leading to higher differences in exit probabilities. This is likely attributed to farms being near retirement (especially without a successor) and experiencing increased competitive pressure, which decreases the incentive to stay in business.	
	Younger and Middle-Aged Groups	Interaction terms with spatial competition indicators reveal no economically substantial different effects on their exit probabilities within these age groups and the no interaction model.	
Legal Form	Sole Proprietorship (family) Farms	Five out of six estimates are statistically and economically significantly associated with all spatial competition indicators	Part-time: Much stronger affected by dominance indicators. They experience the largest difference in exit probability among all legal forms.
	Corporate and Partnership Farms	Show no association at all with any of the spatial competition indicators ; their exit probability differences consistently include zero in the prediction intervals. This suggests they are more resilient to competitive situations in the land market.	
Farm Specializations	Specialist Granivores	Predicted probability differences are similar across all spatial competition indicators, with very low or slightly null associations.	
	Other Specializations	A strong association with the growth indicator often means a weaker or null association with the dominance indicators (and vice versa), highlighting that these are distinct measures of competition with regard to farm specializations.	

FT 2 Specialist Horticulture, **FT 4** **Dominance indicators** have a **larger effect**
Specialist Grazing Livestock, and **FT 5** on exit probabilities **across all farm**
Granivore farms show **non-zero specializations**, except for **FT 2** (inverse)
prediction intervals for exit probability and **FT 5** (low/null association).
differences of the growth indicator. The effect is **often stronger for average**
FT 2 shows the **strongest association** **neighbouring farm size** than the **largest**
with the growth indicator, despite having **neighbour**.
a wide interval. **Strongest associations are found** for **FT 1**
Other specializations include zero in the Specialist Field Crop farms with a nearly
prediction interval, indicating **no** 15%-point difference in exit probability
association with the growth indicator. due to **the average neighbouring farm**
size indicator.
Second strongest associations for **FT 3**
Permanent Crops Farms and **FT 8** Mixed
Crops and Livestock Farms, both showing
over 10%-point differences for **average**
neighbouring farm size indicator.
FT 1, FT 3, and FT 6 Mixed Crops Farms
show the **highest difference** in exit
probability for the **largest neighbour**
indicator.

519 Source: Own compilation.

520 **7 Conclusion**

521 We propose new spatial competition indicators and study how they are associated with farm exit rates across
522 different types of farms. While existing literature finds evidence that spatial interaction between farms matters
523 for farm exit decisions, our findings indicate that spatial competition might not be equally relevant for all types
524 of farms. Specifically, we find that the association between our spatial competition measures and farm exits is

525 particularly strong for the oldest farmers, for full-time and part-time sole proprietorship (family) farms, and some
526 specific farm specializations.

527 For interpreting the results, it needs to be considered that the German FSS locates the data of a farm to the
528 farmstead's address. This means that the spatial competition indicators derived for the neighbourhoods consist
529 of information that is not necessarily part of the area that is supposed to be the neighbourhood. Further, some
530 farms defined as exits might be rather merged with other farms, but the survey does not reveal this information.
531 Future research could explore whether other farm survey data, for instance, Integrated Administration and
532 Control System (IACS) data, could be used for studying spatial competition. While this data might provide finer
533 spatial information, it does not match our dataset in terms of temporal coverage, being easily available Germany-
534 wide and providing detailed farm-level information.

535 Our findings suggest that farms are not all alike with respect to spatial competition and may act and behave
536 differently depending on the competitive situation in the land market. As the fixed availability of agricultural land
537 and the resulting interactions on the land market are defining elements of the agricultural sector, our results are
538 important for research studying land markets and farm structural change, as well as policies with direct or
539 indirect effects on land markets.

540 **8 References**

541 Bakker, M. M., Heuvelink, G. B. M., Vrugt, J. A., Polman, N., Brookhuis, B., and Kuhlman, T. (2018). A numerical
542 method to account for distance in a farmer's willingness to pay for land. *Spatial Statistics* 25: 22–34.

543 Breustedt, G., and Glauben, T. (2007). Driving Forces behind Exiting from Farming in Western Europe. *Journal of*
544 *Agricultural Economics* 58: 115–127.

545 Ciaian, P., and Swinnen, J. F. M. (2006). Land Market Imperfections and Agricultural Policy Impacts in the New
546 EU Member States: A Partial Equilibrium Analysis. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 88: 799–
547 815.

548 Corsi, A., Frontuto, V., and Novelli, S. (2021). What Drives Farm Structural Change? An Analysis of Economic,
549 Demographic and Succession Factors. *Agriculture 11*: 438.

550 Dong, F., Hennessy, D. A., Jensen, H. H., and Volpe, R. J. (2016). Technical efficiency, herd size, and exit intentions
551 in U.S. dairy farms. *Agricultural Economics 47*: 533–545.

552 EIP-AGRI Focus Group. (2016). *New entrants into farming: lessons to foster innovation and entrepreneurship* ,
553 Final Report.

554 Foltz, J. D. (2004). Entry, Exit, and Farm Size: Assessing an Experiment in Dairy Price Policy. *American Journal of*
555 *Agricultural Economics 86*: 594–604.

556 Goddard, E., Weersink, A., Chen, K., and Turvey, C. G. (1993). Economics of Structural Change in Agriculture.
557 *Canadian Journal of Agricultural Economics/Revue Canadienne d'agroeconomie 41*: 475–489.

558 Grammatikopoulou, I., Myyrä, S., and Pouta, E. (2013). The proximity of a field plot and land-use choice:
559 implications for land consolidation. *Journal of Land Use Science 8*: 383–402.

560 Graubner, M., Ostapchuk, I., and Gagalyuk, T. (2021). Agroholdings and land rental markets: a spatial competition
561 perspective. *European Review of Agricultural Economics 48*: 158–206.

562 Hoppe, R. A., and Korb, P. J. (2006). *Understanding U.S. Farm Exits* , Economic Reserach Report No. 21; Economic
563 Research Service. United States Department of Agriculture , 42. DOI: 10.22004/ag.econ.7212 , last
564 accessed

565 Huettel, S., and Margarian, A. (2009). Structural change in the West German agricultural sector. *Agricultural*
566 *Economics 40*: 759–772.

567 Jänicke, C., and Müller, D. (2024). Revealing agricultural land ownership concentration with cadastral and
568 company network data. *Agriculture and Human Values* .

569 Kay, S., Peuch, J., and Franco, J. (2015). *Extent of farmland grabbing in the EU*. LU: Publications Office.

570 Kitenge, E. (2022). Determinants of entries into and exits from the US farming sector. *The Quarterly Review of*
571 *Economics and Finance 85*: 379–385.

572 Landi, C., Stefani, G., Rocchi, B., Lombardi, G. V., and Giampaolo, S. (2016). Regional Differentiation and Farm
573 Exit: A Hierarchical Model for Tuscany. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 67: 208–230.

574 Latruffe, L., and Piet, L. (2014). Does land fragmentation affect farm performance? A case study from Brittany,
575 France. *Agricultural Systems* 129: 68–80.

576 Machl, T. (2016). Entwicklung eines Werkzeugs zur landesweit flächendeckenden Analyse landwirtschaftlicher
577 Transportbeziehungen in Bayern. *zfv – Zeitschrift für Geodäsie, Geoinformation und Landmanagement*
578 3/2016: 197–205.

579 Mishra, A. K., El-Osta, H. S., and Shaik, S. (2010). Succession Decisions in U.S. Family Farm Businesses. *Journal of*
580 *Agricultural and Resource Economics* 35: 133–152.

581 Paroissien, E., Latruffe, L., and Piet, L. (2021). Early exit from business, performance and neighbours' influence: a
582 study of farmers in France. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 48: 1132–1161.

583 Pennerstorfer, D. (2022). Farm exits and competition on the land market: Evidence from spatially explicit data.
584 *Working Paper No. 2209*.

585 Piet, L., Latruffe, L., Le Mouël, C., and Desjeux, Y. (2012). How do agricultural policies influence farm size
586 inequality? The example of France. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 39: 5–28.

587 Plogmann, J., Mußhoff, O., Odening, M., and Ritter, M. (2022). Farm growth and land concentration. *Land Use*
588 *Policy* 115: 106036.

589 Ramsey, A. F., Ghosh, S. K., and Sonoda, T. (2019). Saying Sayonara to the Farm: Hierarchical Bayesian Modeling
590 of Farm Exits in Japan. *Journal of Agricultural Economics* 70: 372–391.

591 Saint-Cyr, L. D. F., Storm, H., Heckelei, T., and Piet, L. (2019). Heterogeneous impacts of neighbouring farm size
592 on the decision to exit: evidence from Brittany. *European Review of Agricultural Economics* 46: 237–266.

593 Statistisches Bundesamt. (2021). *Landwirtschaftliche Betriebe insgesamt und Betriebe mit ökologischem Landbau*
594 *nach Bundesländern - Statistisches Bundesamt. Landwirtschaftliche Betriebe.*
595 <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Branchen-Unternehmen/Landwirtschaft-Forstwirtschaft->

596 Fischerei/Landwirtschaftliche-Betriebe/Tabellen/oekologischer-landbau-bundeslaender.html , last
597 accessed 13 December 2022.

598 Storm, H., Mittenzwei, K., and Heckelei, T. (2015). Direct Payments, Spatial Competition, and Farm Survival in
599 Norway. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 97: 1192–1205.

600 Viira, A.-H., Pöder, A., and Värnik, R. (2013). The Determinants of Farm Growth, Decline and Exit in Estonia.
601 *German Journal of Agricultural Economics* 62Article 1.

602 Weiss, C. R. (1999). Farm Growth and Survival: Econometric Evidence for Individual Farms in Upper Austria.
603 *American Journal of Agricultural Economics* 81: 103–116.

604 Zorn, A., and Zimmert, F. (2022). Structural change in the dairy sector: exit from farming and farm type change.
605 *Agricultural and Food Economics* 10: 7.

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9 Data sources

Table 7. Overview of data sources used

Data	Notes	Source
German Farm Structure Survey	German Farm Structure Survey data for 1999 - 2007	RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0; AFID-Panel farm structure 1999/2001/2003/2005/2007, On-Site-Access.
German Farm Structure Survey	German Farm Structure Survey data for 2010 - 2020	RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2020.00.01.1.1.0; AFID-Panel farm structure 2010/2013/2016/2020, On-Site-Access.)
Standard gross margins	Derived from an API of Kuratorium für Technik und Bauwesen in der Landwirtschaft e.V. (KTBL) website.	https://www.ktbl.de/webanwendungen/standarddeckungsbeitraege
Unemployment rate		Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting at: https://statistik.arbeitsagentur.de/SiteGlobals/Forms/Suche/Einzelheftsuc he_Formular.html?topic_f=gemeinde-arbeitslose-quoten&dateOfRevision=199812-202206
Compensation of employees		Federal and state statistical offices. Working group: National accounts, at: https://www.statistikportal.de/de/vgrdl/ergebnisse-kreisebene/einkommen-kreise - vgrdl_r2b2_bs2020.xlsx
Disposable income		Federal and state statistical offices. Working group: National accounts, at: https://www.statistikportal.de/de/vgrdl/ergebnisse-kreisebene/einkommen-kreise - vgrdl_r2b3_bs2020.xlsx
Population density	Population density per square kilometre	Federal and state statistical offices. Dataset ID: AI002-1 at: www.regionalstatistik.de

Source: Own compilation.

A Appendix

A.1 Descriptive statistics

The farm level descriptive statistics are measured in 2010 and regional variables are measured as averages between 2008 and around 2020. All descriptive statistics are differentiated by the farm's exit status in 2020. The continuous variables are provided with their mean and standard deviation, and the differences between the exit status are also reported. For the categorical variables, the number of farms for both staying and exiting farms are presented. The farm level variables average growth rate of agricultural land use and livestock units are derived over the time span from 1999 to 2010. These averages are calculated using data from the years 1999, 2003, 2007, and 2010, provided that the farm was surveyed in any of these years. The standard gross margins are calculated as the sum of all standard gross margins of the farm's activities, with activity-specific values derived from KTBL as averages over the years 2008 to 2018. The NUTS 3 regional variables, categorized as "Regional variables at NUTS 3", are also averages over a time span from 2008 and later. Specifically, the compensation of employees and the disposable income are averaged over the years 2008 to 2019, while the population density is averaged from 2008 to 2020, and the unemployment rate is averaged from 2008 to 2022.

Table 8. Descriptive statistics of continues variables in 2010

Category	Variable	Mean (sd) of staying	Mean (sd) of	Difference	P-value
Farm level	Average growth rate of agricultural land	2.58 (21.13)	-0.87 (11.68)	-3.46	0
	Average growth rate of livestock units	0.75 (22.75)	-2.09 (22.17)	-2.83	0
	Land rental payments for total	193.76 (544.18)	163.45	-30.31	0
	Livestock units	50.91 (116.96)	18.80 (89.90)	-32.11	0
	Ratio of rented land on total agricultural	37.95 (31.96)	26.79 (33.63)	-11.16	0
	Standard gross margin of the farm	104,665.34	44,602.69	-60,062.65	0.063
	Total agricultural land used (hectare)	65.34 (168.00)	24.61 (55.88)	-40.74	0

	Total agricultural land used squared	32,495.21	3,728.28	-28,766.93	0.311
Regional	Compensation of employees (1,000 €) -	31.58 (3.29)	31.58 (3.54)	-0.01	0.368
variable at	Compensation of employees (1,000 €) -	44.16 (6.97)	44.18 (7.22)	0.02	0.272
NUTS 3	Disposable income of private households	21,082.35 (1,959.42)	20,971.82	-110.53	0
	Population density per square kilometre	214.88 (273.82)	247.80 (374.02)	32.92	0
	Unemployment rate	4.61 (2.06)	4.78 (2.08)	0.17	0

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Table 9. Descriptive statistics of farm-level interacted categorical variables in 2010

Category	Specializations/Subclass	Number (%) of staying farms	Number (%) of exiting farms
Farm specializations	field crops	52,112 (71.1%)	21,188 (28.9%)
	horticulture	4,773 (57.8%)	3,485 (42.2%)
	permanent crops	15,088 (64.5%)	8,309 (35.5%)
	grazing livestock	104,355 (80.4%)	25,473 (19.6%)
	granivores	15,718 (81.5%)	3,567 (18.5%)
	cropping	3,113 (81.3%)	717 (18.7%)
	livestock holdings	8,988 (84.9%)	1,601 (15.1%)
	crops — livestock	25,217 (82.3%)	5,430 (17.7%)
Legal form	full-time	111,045 (82.0%)	24,367 (18.0%)
	part-time	96,296 (70.0%)	41,322 (30.0%)
	Corporate farm	4,126 (81.5%)	936 (18.5%)
	Partnership farm	17,897 (85.1%)	3,145 (14.9%)
Age of farm holder	<= 40	45,082 (81.6%)	10,154 (18.4%)
	40 < years <= 55	129,887 (82.2%)	28,221 (17.8%)
	> 55	54,395 (63.4%)	31,395 (36.6%)

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

Table 10. Descriptive statistics of remaining farm level categorical variables in 2010

Category	Variable	Number (%) of staying	Number (%) of exiting
	Agricultural vocational training	65,127 (69.3%)	28,871 (30.7%)

Education	Vocational school/vocational college (without company-	11,753 (68.8%)	5,320 (31.2%)
	Vocational training/apprenticeship (with final	36,740 (76.4%)	11,347 (23.6%)
	One-year technical school, agricultural school	43,871 (79.0%)	11,688 (21.0%)
	Further training as foreman, specialist agronomist	37,654 (84.6%)	6,857 (15.4%)
	Secondary agricultural school, technical school, two-	17,536 (88.8%)	2,209 (11.2%)
	Degree with less than 4 years standard period of study	9,025 (82.9%)	1,868 (17.1%)
	Degree with at least 4 years standard period of study	7,658 (82.6%)	1,610 (17.4%)
Productive orientation	Organic farm	13,960 (84.4%)	2,572 (15.6%)
	Conventional farm	215,404 (76.2%)	67,198 (23.8%)

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI:

10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

Table 11. Descriptive statistics of NUTS 2 categorical variables in 2010

Variable	Number (%) of staying farms	Number (%) of exiting farms
Schleswig-Holstein	10,365 (69.6%)	4,534 (30.4%)
Braunschweig	3,579 (76.4%)	1,103 (23.6%)
Hannover	5,357 (74.9%)	1,792 (25.1%)
Lüneburg	8,761 (75.6%)	2,822 (24.4%)
Weser-Ems	13,676 (74.0%)	4,801 (26.0%)
Düsseldorf	4,037 (74.9%)	1,351 (25.1%)
Köln	4,374 (75.7%)	1,401 (24.3%)
Münster	8,242 (77.3%)	2,420 (22.7%)
Detmold	5,867 (75.3%)	1,921 (24.7%)
Arnsberg	4,828 (78.7%)	1,309 (21.3%)
Darmstadt	4,378 (75.7%)	1,402 (24.3%)
Gießen	3,343 (75.0%)	1,113 (25.0%)
Kassel	5,684 (75.1%)	1,885 (24.9%)
Koblenz	4,689 (73.2%)	1,717 (26.8%)
Trier	3,714 (71.3%)	1,494 (28.7%)
Rheinhessen-Pfalz	6,196 (69.2%)	2,754 (30.8%)
Stuttgart	10,965 (76.2%)	3,432 (23.8%)
Karlsruhe	3,798 (77.0%)	1,132 (23.0%)
Freiburg	10,475 (77.0%)	3,136 (23.0%)
Tübingen	9,322 (80.5%)	2,252 (19.5%)
Oberbayern	21,142 (83.7%)	4,104 (16.3%)
Niederbayern	13,208 (79.2%)	3,466 (20.8%)
Oberpfalz	9,909 (80.7%)	2,373 (19.3%)
Oberfranken	6,657 (76.5%)	2,045 (23.5%)
Mittelfranken	7,663 (77.1%)	2,275 (22.9%)
Unterfranken	6,885 (74.9%)	2,310 (25.1%)
Schwaben	12,667 (80.0%)	3,169 (20.0%)

Saarland	930 (70.5%)	389 (29.5%)
Brandenburg	4,267 (75.8%)	1,365 (24.2%)
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	3,356 (71.0%)	1,369 (29.0%)
Dresden	2,129 (78.3%)	591 (21.7%)
Chemnitz	1,872 (78.5%)	513 (21.5%)
Leipzig	920 (77.8%)	262 (22.2%)
Sachsen-Anhalt	3,281 (77.8%)	938 (22.2%)
Thüringen	2,828 (77.3%)	830 (22.7%)

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

A.2 Illustration of competition in the land market based on our defined measures

In this section we want to illustrate how the land market competition indicators visually look like. It extends the explanations in Chapter 2. Figure 5 illustrates a growth scenario for a neighbourhood between 1999 and 2010. The first row represents the initial farm sizes in 1999, depicted by the size of the circles. The second row presents three possible outcomes of growth scenarios. Within each circle, the first number indicates the absolute growth, while the second number represents the *Growth1* indicator value. The red circle highlights the farm that serves as the reference point for illustrating the growth scenario. In these scenarios, one or more farms cease to exist, and their land is absorbed by the remaining farms. As more farms disappear, the growth of the remaining farms increases to accommodate the additional land. This is reflected in the indicator values, which rise from low to medium to high growth scenarios.

Figure 5. Illustration of growth scenarios for one neighbourhood from 1999 to 2010 with different growth rates and farm numbers

Source: Own compilation.

The next two figures illustrate the dominance scenarios of six different dominance situations based on the size of the farms in a neighbourhood.

Figure 6. Illustration dominance scenarios in three neighbourhoods with relatively higher dominance situations, with different farm sizes and numbers

Source: Own compilation.

Neighbourhoods 1 and 3 illustrate a dominant (highly competitive) land market situation. According to our indicators, the six smaller farms in neighbourhood 1 receive relatively high values for both land market dominance indicators, indicating higher competitive pressure. In contrast, the largest farm in these neighbourhoods receives a very low value for each dominance indicator, reflecting its dominant position in the land market with minimal competition from neighbouring farms.

Figure 7. Illustration dominance scenarios in three neighbourhoods with relatively lower dominance situations, with different farm sizes and numbers

Source: Own compilation.

Neighbourhoods 2 and 4 differ somewhat from the others in terms of land market structure. Neighbourhood 5 is diverse but lacks truly dominant farms, while in neighbourhood 6, all farms are of equal size. In neighbourhood 5, values for both dominance indicators are relatively evenly distributed. However, the largest farm has a $Domi2_{in}$ value of 0.71 and a $Domi3_{in}$ value of 1, whereas the smallest farm has the highest values of 1.58 and 2, respectively. Overall, the competitive situation based on farm size is captured well. Still, the extremes in dominance values are notably different from those in neighbourhoods 1 and 3, where smaller farms experience much stronger competitive pressure.

A.3 Predicted probability curves at the 10th and 90th percentiles of the dependent variable

In this section, the predicted probability curves are presented and further illustrate how the predicted exit probabilities are changing with the spatial competition indicator values. For each spatial competition indicator, a separate figure is presented and heterogenous effects for three age groups, four legal forms and eight farm

specializations are considered. The figures presenting the predicted probability curves have four rows and columns, respectively. The first row consists of the predicted probabilities for the “no interaction” and “age groups” interaction model, the second row shows it for the “legal forms” and the third and fourth row for the “farm specializations”. For all farm types considered, one can see that the predicted exit probabilities are diverging in slope and level. For better comparison the x-axis is the same across all separate plots, which mirror the 10th and 90th percentiles of population values of each spatial competition indicator. However, to reflect the different range of values for each of the age, legal form, or farm specialization categories, dashed lines indicate the 10th and the dot-dashed lines the 90th percentiles of the spatial competition indicator values of each specific category. If those lines are not drawn, they are outside of the presented range of values. For instance, the range of the values of the growth of the others (*Growth1*) indicator used for prediction of exit probabilities are too narrow for the horticulture farm specialization, as no dashed and dot-dashed lines are drawn. For mixed livestock holdings, the range is very well depicted. Probability curves outside the range of 10th and 90th percentiles are generated supposing the estimated associations hold also outside of the observed range for this specific farm type, hence, effects need to be interpreted with extra caution.

The predicted probability curves effectively illustrate the level and slope of the exit probability for each spatial competition indicator across the various farm types considered. Notably, the level of exit probability falls within a similar range for the different farm types across the spatial competition indicators. However, certain farm types exhibit distinct exit probability patterns. Specifically, the oldest age group (farmers over 55 years), corporate farms, and horticulture farms, followed by permanent crop farms, display the highest and above-average base exit probabilities. In contrast, mixed specialized farms (FT 7 and 8) and farmers under 55 years of age show lower-than-average exit probabilities.

A.3.1 Growth indicator “growth of the others” (*Growth1*)

Examining the age groups, the exit probability is increasing with *Growth1* similarly.

Dashed lines show 10th and dot-dashed the 90th percentiles of farm type specific values. Prediction based on pseudo weighted country average.

Figure 8. Predicted probabilities for the no interaction and interaction effects of the Growth1 indicator

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

Corporate and partnership farms exhibit a slightly decreasing exit probability, although the economic amount of this change is relatively small. On the other hand, family farms show an increasing exit probability.

For the farm specializations, specialist horticulture (FT 2) farms have the highest increase in exit probability when the growth indicator *Growth1* is increasing. Permanent crop farms (FT 3) and mixed livestock farms (FT 7) do not show much different exit probabilities across the range of *Growth1*. The other specializations show a more pronounced but very low increase in the exit probability when *Growth1* increases.

A.3.2 Dominance indicator “average size of neighbouring farms” (*Domi2*)

Dashed lines show 10th and dot-dashed the 90th percentiles of farm type specific values. Prediction based on pseudo weighted country average.

Figure 9. Predicted probabilities for the no interaction and interaction effects of the *Domi2* indicator

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI:

10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

For all farm types considered, one can see that the predicted exit probabilities are diverging in slope across the spatial competition indicator range. Regarding the age groups, the increase with *Domi2* is fairly the same within the age groups and similar to *Growth1*.

Examining legal forms, the corporate and partnership farms have no or only a slightly increasing exit probability, whereas the family farms have a much more pronounced increase of exit probabilities.

For the farm specializations, specialist horticulture (FT 2) farms have the lowest increase in exit probability when *Domi2* is increasing. The specialist field crops, mixed crops livestock and permanent crop farms (FT1, 8 and 3) have the highest increase in exit probability across the range of values of *Domi2*.

A.3.3 Dominance indicator “largest neighbouring farm” (*Domi3*)

For all farm types considered, and comparable to the other spatial competition indicators, the predicted exit probabilities are diverging in slope and level. Considering the age groups, the exit probability is increasing with *Domi3*, similar with *Growth1* and *Domi2*.

Inspecting the legal forms, the corporate farms show no economically significant increasing in exit probability and full-time family and partnership farms show a more pronounced increase, whereas the part-time family farms have a much stronger increase of exit probabilities.

For specialist horticulture (FT 2) farms the exit probability when *Domi3* is increasing is lowest. The specialist field crops, mixed cropping and permanent crop farms (FT1, 6 and 3) have the highest increase in exit probability across the range of values of *Domi3*.

Dashed lines show 10th and dot-dashed the 90th percentiles of farm type specific values. Prediction based on pseudo weighted country average.

Figure 10. Predicted probabilities for the no-interaction and interaction effects of the Dom3 indicator

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0.

A.4 Predicted probability difference in percentage points at the 10th and 90th percentiles of the dependent variable

In this chapter, we present the predicted probability differences in percentage points at the 10th and 90th percentiles of each of the variables considered in the models. First, a table shows it for the “no interaction” and the interaction models, followed by figures of the predicted probability percentage point differences. The predicted probability differences of the variables other than the spatial competition indicators should not be interpreted as they serve as control variables.

A.4.1 Growth indicator “growth of the others” *Growth1*

Table 12. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “growth of the others” *Growth1* model

Description	Category	“Growth of the others” <i>Growth1</i> model			
		Homogenous	Age groups	Legal form	Farm specialization
Growth1	Neighbouring variable	2.62% [0.33%; 4.92%]	-	-	-
Growth1 - Age category 1) years <= 40	Neighbouring variable	-	2.84% [0.77%; 4.90%]	-	-
Growth1 - Age category 2) 40 < years <= 55	Neighbouring variable	-	1.95% [0.02%; 3.87%]	-	-
Growth1 - Age category 3) years > 55	Neighbouring variable	-	3.54% [0.50%; 6.58%]	-	-
Growth1 - 1) Sole proprietorship farm (full-time)	Neighbouring variable	-	-	3.78% [1.82%; 5.74%]	-
Growth1 - 2) Sole proprietorship farm (part-time)	Neighbouring variable	-	-	2.12% [0.02%; 4.21%]	-
Growth1 - 3) Corporate farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-1.15% [-5.18%; 2.88%]	-
Growth1 - 4) Partnership farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-0.86% [-3.11%; 1.39%]	-
Growth1 - FT 1 Specialist field crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.04% [-0.32%; 4.40%]
Growth1 - FT 2 Specialist horticulture	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	8.33% [4.86%; 11.81%]
Growth1 - FT 3 Specialist permanent crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	-0.17% [-3.03%; 2.69%]
Growth1 - FT 4 Specialist grazing livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.84% [0.90%; 4.78%]
Growth1 - FT 5 Specialist granivores	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	3.08% [0.47%; 5.68%]
Growth1 - FT 6 Mixed cropping	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.88% [-0.32%; 6.08%]

Growth1 - FT 7 Mixed livestock holdings	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	0.76% [-1.48%; 3.00%]
Growth1 - FT 8 Mixed crops — livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.00% [-0.01%; 4.00%]
Total agricultural land used (hectare)	Farm level	-12.94% [-15.23%; -10.66%]	-12.94% [-15.23%; -10.66%]	-12.91% [-15.21%; -10.62%]	-13.01% [-15.30%; -10.71%]
Ratio of rented land on total agricultural land	Farm level	-4.46% [-6.73%; -2.19%]	-4.46% [-6.73%; -2.19%]	-4.46% [-6.74%; -2.18%]	-4.47% [-6.75%; -2.19%]
Land rental payments for total agricultural land per hectare	Farm level	-0.23% [-2.50%; 2.05%]	-0.23% [-2.50%; 2.05%]	-0.23% [-2.52%; 2.06%]	-0.23% [-2.51%; 2.06%]
Livestock units	Farm level	-5.28% [-7.55%; -3.01%]	-5.28% [-7.55%; -3.01%]	-5.27% [-7.56%; -2.99%]	-5.21% [-7.49%; -2.92%]
Standard gross margin of the farm	Farm level	-4.88% [-7.16%; -2.60%]	-4.88% [-7.16%; -2.60%]	-4.91% [-7.20%; -2.62%]	-4.96% [-7.25%; -2.66%]
Average growth rate of agricultural land use	Farm level	-2.90% [-5.17%; -0.64%]	-2.90% [-5.17%; -0.63%]	-2.87% [-5.15%; -0.59%]	-2.90% [-5.19%; -0.62%]
Average growth rate of livestock units	Farm level	-1.49% [-3.77%; 0.79%]	-1.49% [-3.77%; 0.79%]	-1.47% [-3.77%; 0.82%]	-1.50% [-3.80%; 0.79%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Service sector	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-1.08% [-3.39%; 1.22%]	-1.09% [-3.39%; 1.22%]	-1.09% [-3.41%; 1.23%]	-1.07% [-3.39%; 1.25%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Manufacturing sector	Regional variable at NUTS 3	0.02% [-2.30%; 2.34%]	0.02% [-2.30%; 2.34%]	0.00% [-2.33%; 2.33%]	-0.02% [-2.35%; 2.32%]
Unemployment rate	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-1.72% [-4.05%; 0.60%]	-1.72% [-4.04%; 0.61%]	-1.67% [-4.01%; 0.67%]	-1.73% [-4.07%; 0.61%]
Population density per square kilometer	Regional variable at NUTS 3	1.41% [-0.89%; 3.70%]	1.41% [-0.89%; 3.70%]	1.40% [-0.91%; 3.70%]	1.38% [-0.92%; 3.69%]
Disposable income of private households (€)	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-1.98% [-4.30%; 0.35%]	-1.97% [-4.30%; 0.35%]	-1.92% [-4.26%; 0.41%]	-1.98% [-4.32%; 0.36%]

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 11. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “growth of the others” *Growth1*

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 12. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “growth of the others” *Growth1* - Age groups model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 13. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “growth of the others” *Growth1* - Legal form model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 14. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “growth of the others” *Growth1* - Farm specialization model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

A.4.2 Dominance indicator “average neighbouring farm size” *Domi2*

Table 13. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “average neighbouring farm size” *Domi2*

Description	Category	“Average neighbouring farm size” <i>Domi2</i> model			
		Homogenous	Age groups	Legal form	Farm specialization
Domi2	Neighbouring variable	3.56% [1.28%; 5.84%]	-	-	-
Domi2 - Age category 1) years <= 40	Neighbouring variable	-	3.10% [1.10%; 5.10%]	-	-
Domi2 - Age category 2) 40 < years <= 55	Neighbouring variable	-	2.88% [1.00%; 4.75%]	-	-
Domi2 - Age category 3) years > 55	Neighbouring variable	-	4.82% [1.77%; 7.88%]	-	-
Domi2 - 1) Sole proprietorship farm (full-time)	Neighbouring variable	-	-	2.67% [0.74%; 4.61%]	-
Domi2 - 2) Sole proprietorship farm (part-time)	Neighbouring variable	-	-	7.41% [5.22%; 9.59%]	-
Domi2 - 3) Corporate farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	0.75% [-2.87%; 4.37%]	-
Domi2 - 4) Partnership farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	1.87% [-0.15%; 3.90%]	-
Domi2 - FT 1 Specialist field crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	14.14% [11.22%; 17.06%]
Domi2 - FT 2 Specialist horticulture	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	1.35% [-1.96%; 4.66%]
Domi2 - FT 3 Specialist permanent crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	10.97% [8.31%; 13.63%]
Domi2 - FT 4 Specialist grazing livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	8.35% [6.20%; 10.51%]
Domi2 - FT 5 Specialist granivores	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.25% [-0.05%; 4.56%]
Domi2 - FT 6 Mixed cropping	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	8.61% [4.97%; 12.25%]

Domi2 - FT 7 Mixed livestock holdings	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	8.01% [5.19%; 10.83%]
Domi2 - FT 8 Mixed crops — livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	11.83% [8.96%; 14.71%]
Total agricultural land used (hectare)	Farm level	-10.51% [-12.72%; -8.30%]	-10.51% [-12.72%; -8.30%]	-11.03% [-13.30%; -8.76%]	-9.22% [-11.50%; -6.94%]
Ratio of rented land on total agricultural land	Farm level	-3.79% [-5.99%; -1.60%]	-3.79% [-5.99%; -1.60%]	-3.86% [-6.12%; -1.61%]	-3.84% [-6.11%; -1.57%]
Land rental payments for total agricultural land per hectare	Farm level	-0.19% [-2.39%; 2.01%]	-0.19% [-2.39%; 2.01%]	-0.18% [-2.44%; 2.08%]	-0.16% [-2.44%; 2.12%]
Livestock units	Farm level	-6.54% [-8.71%; -4.36%]	-6.54% [-8.71%; -4.36%]	-5.96% [-8.20%; -3.71%]	-6.22% [-8.48%; -3.96%]
Standard gross margin of the farm	Farm level	-4.24% [-6.45%; -2.04%]	-4.24% [-6.45%; -2.04%]	-4.09% [-6.35%; -1.82%]	-4.59% [-6.88%; -2.31%]
Average growth rate of agricultural land use	Farm level	-2.78% [-4.97%; -0.59%]	-2.78% [-4.97%; -0.58%]	-2.78% [-5.03%; -0.53%]	-2.70% [-4.97%; -0.44%]
Average growth rate of livestock units	Farm level	-1.20% [-3.40%; 1.00%]	-1.20% [-3.40%; 1.00%]	-1.40% [-3.67%; 0.86%]	-1.39% [-3.67%; 0.90%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Service sector	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-1.09% [-3.32%; 1.14%]	-1.09% [-3.32%; 1.14%]	-1.10% [-3.38%; 1.19%]	-1.09% [-3.39%; 1.22%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Manufacturing	Regional variable at NUTS 3	0.12% [-2.12%; 2.36%]	0.12% [-2.12%; 2.36%]	0.04% [-2.26%; 2.34%]	-0.04% [-2.36%; 2.28%]
Unemployment rate	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-2.73% [-4.97%; -0.49%]	-2.73% [-4.97%; -0.49%]	-2.83% [-5.13%; -0.53%]	-3.05% [-5.37%; -0.72%]
Population density per square kilometer	Regional variable at NUTS 3	1.56% [-0.65%; 3.78%]	1.56% [-0.65%; 3.78%]	1.61% [-0.67%; 3.89%]	1.65% [-0.65%; 3.94%]
Disposable income of private households (€)	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-2.11% [-4.36%; 0.13%]	-2.11% [-4.36%; 0.13%]	-2.10% [-4.40%; 0.21%]	-2.07% [-4.40%; 0.25%]

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 15. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “average neighbouring farm size” *Domi2*

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 16. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “average neighbouring farm size” Domi2

- Age groups model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 17. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “average neighbouring farm size” *Domi2*

- Legal form model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 18. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “average neighbouring farm size” *Domi2*
- Farm specialization model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

A.4.3 Dominance indicator “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3*

Table 14. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3*

Description	Category	“Largest neighbouring farm” <i>Domi3</i> model			
		Homogenous	Age groups	Legal form	Farm specialization
Domi3	Neighbouring variable	3.01% [0.73%; 5.28%]	-	-	-
Domi3 - Age category 1) years <= 40	Neighbouring variable	-	2.29% [0.31%; 4.27%]	-	-
Domi3 - Age category 2) 40 < years <= 55	Neighbouring variable	-	2.51% [0.64%; 4.39%]	-	-
Domi3 - Age category 3) years > 55	Neighbouring variable	-	4.17% [1.13%; 7.20%]	-	-
Domi3 - 1) Sole proprietorship farm (full-	Neighbouring variable	-	-	1.80% [-0.10%; 3.70%]	-
Domi3 - 2) Sole proprietorship farm (part-	Neighbouring variable	-	-	6.00% [3.85%; 8.14%]	-
Domi3 - 3) Corporate farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	0.93% [-2.63%; 4.49%]	-
Domi3 - 4) Partnership farm	Neighbouring variable	-	-	1.61% [-0.41%; 3.62%]	-
Domi3 - FT 1 Specialist field crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	9.55% [6.75%; 12.34%]
Domi3 - FT 2 Specialist horticulture	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	0.86% [-2.39%; 4.11%]
Domi3 - FT 3 Specialist permanent crops	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	9.13% [6.63%; 11.64%]
Domi3 - FT 4 Specialist grazing livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	6.45% [4.35%; 8.55%]
Domi3 - FT 5 Specialist granivores	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	2.48% [0.17%; 4.79%]
Domi3 - FT 6 Mixed cropping	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	8.85% [5.06%; 12.64%]

Domi3 - FT 7 Mixed livestock holdings	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	5.66% [3.11%; 8.21%]
Domi3 - FT 8 Mixed crops — livestock	Neighbouring variable	-	-	-	7.48% [4.83%; 10.13%]
Total agricultural land used (hectare)	Farm level	-11.25% [-13.46%; -9.04%]	-11.25% [-13.46%; -9.04%]	-11.68% [-13.94%; -9.43%]	-10.51% [-12.76%; -8.26%]
Ratio of rented land on total agricultural land	Farm level	-3.90% [-6.09%; -1.70%]	-3.89% [-6.09%; -1.70%]	-3.92% [-6.16%; -1.69%]	-3.87% [-6.11%; -1.63%]
Land rental payments for total agricultural land per Livestock units	Farm level	-0.20% [-2.40%; 2.00%]	-0.20% [-2.40%; 2.00%]	-0.19% [-2.43%; 2.05%]	-0.16% [-2.41%; 2.08%]
Standard gross margin of the farm	Farm level	-4.24% [-6.45%; -2.04%]	-4.24% [-6.44%; -2.03%]	-4.16% [-6.41%; -1.92%]	-4.41% [-6.66%; -2.16%]
Average growth rate of agricultural land use	Farm level	-2.81% [-5.00%; -0.61%]	-2.81% [-5.00%; -0.61%]	-2.82% [-5.05%; -0.59%]	-2.77% [-5.01%; -0.54%]
Average growth rate of livestock units	Farm level	-1.27% [-3.47%; 0.94%]	-1.26% [-3.47%; 0.94%]	-1.40% [-3.64%; 0.85%]	-1.34% [-3.59%; 0.91%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Service sector	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-1.07% [-3.30%; 1.16%]	-1.07% [-3.30%; 1.16%]	-1.10% [-3.36%; 1.17%]	-1.09% [-3.36%; 1.18%]
Compensation of employees (1,000 €) - Manufacturing	Regional variable at NUTS 3	0.14% [-2.10%; 2.38%]	0.14% [-2.10%; 2.38%]	0.08% [-2.20%; 2.36%]	0.01% [-2.27%; 2.30%]
Unemployment rate	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-2.16% [-4.40%; 0.09%]	-2.16% [-4.40%; 0.09%]	-2.13% [-4.42%; 0.16%]	-2.19% [-4.48%; 0.10%]
Population density per square kilometer	Regional variable at NUTS 3	1.41% [-0.80%; 3.63%]	1.42% [-0.80%; 3.63%]	1.44% [-0.82%; 3.70%]	1.49% [-0.78%; 3.75%]
Disposable income of private households (€)	Regional variable at NUTS 3	-2.11% [-4.36%; 0.13%]	-2.11% [-4.36%; 0.13%]	-2.11% [-4.40%; 0.18%]	-2.11% [-4.40%; 0.18%]

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 19. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3*

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 20. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3* - Age groups model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 21. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3* - Legal form model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.

Figure 22. Predicted probability difference in percentage points for “largest neighbouring farm” *Domi3* - Farm specialization model

Source: Own compilation. RDC of the Federal Statistical Office and Statistical Offices of the Federal States of Germany, DOI: 10.21242/41121.2007.00.01.1.1.0 and DOI: 10.21242/41121.2023.00.01.1.1.0. Federal Employment Agency Statistics / Labour Market Reporting. Federal and state statistical offices.